

Dual Shapiro steps and fundamental transconductance in dc driven Bloch transistor

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I. The eigenvalue equation in the matrix form

The eigenvalue equation for the bare Hamiltonian of the Bloch transistor has the form [1]

$$\left[4E_c \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \chi^2} + E_J(\phi) \cos \chi + E \right] \psi = 0, \quad (1)$$

where E_c is the charging energy and $E_J(\phi)$ is the Josephson energy, i.e.,

$$E_J(\phi) = \left(E_{J1}^2 + E_{J2}^2 + 2E_{J1}E_{J2} \cos \phi \right)^{1/2}. \quad (2)$$

Here E_{J1} and E_{J2} are Josephson energies of individual Josephson junctions. The wave function in Eq. (1) has the form [2]:

$$\Psi_q^{(\phi)}(\chi) = w_q^{(\phi)}(\chi) e^{i\chi q/2e} = w_q^{(\phi)}(\chi) e^{i\kappa\chi}, \quad (3)$$

where w stands for the Bloch wave amplitude and $\kappa = q/2e$ is the dimensionless Bloch vector (crystal momentum). The wave function (3) can be represented as a superposition of an infinite number of plane waves $e^{i\kappa\chi}$, $e^{i(\kappa\pm 1)\chi}$, $e^{i(\kappa\pm 2)\chi}$, ... with complex coefficients (weights). Then the operator [...] on the left-hand side of Eq.(1) in the matrix form reads:

$$B = \begin{pmatrix} \dots & \Lambda & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \Lambda & x - (k-4)^2 & \Lambda & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \Lambda & x - (k-2)^2 & \Lambda & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \Lambda & x - k^2 & \Lambda & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \Lambda & x - (k+2)^2 & \Lambda & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \Lambda & x - (k+4)^2 & \Lambda \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \Lambda & \dots \end{pmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

where $x = E/E_c$ is the unknown value, $k = 2\kappa$, the double Bloch vector, and $\Lambda = E_J(\phi)/2E_c$, the half-ratio of the Josephson and charging energies. The diagonal elements (central element B_{00} is marked by red color for clarity) stem from the first and the third terms in Eq.(1), while the off-diagonal terms Λ are due to the second (Josephson-coupling) term, i.e., $E_J(\phi) \cos \chi = 0.5 E_J(\phi) (e^{i\chi} + e^{-i\chi})$. For given values of variables k and ϕ , the needed eigenvalue x is the root of equation

$$\det B(x) = 0. \quad (5)$$

Note, that in our extended zone scheme, the root, found for the Bloch-vector values, lying within the basic range, $-1 < \kappa < 1$, corresponds to the needed ground state energy, i.e., $E = E_0(q, \phi)$. Equation (5) is solved numerically.

II. Algorithm for finding the ground state energy $E_0(q, \phi)$

Firstly, we truncate matrix B_{ij} (4) such that the range of both integer indexes is limited, i.e., $-N_{\max} \leq i, j \leq N_{\max}$. For not very large ratio E_J/E_c (i.e., not a tight-binding limit [2]), integer number N_{\max} , giving an accurate result,

is not very large. Empirically, parameter N_{\max} can be chosen such, that further increase of N_{\max} does not notably change the obtained result.

For fixed values of q and ϕ , numerical solving Eq.(5) is based on the bisection method. Using evenness and periodicity of function E_0 , i.e.,

$$E_0(q, \phi) = E_0(-q, \phi) = E_0(q, -\phi) \quad \text{and} \quad E_0(q, \phi) = E_0(q + 2e, \phi) = E_0(q, \phi + 2\pi), \quad (6)$$

we can limit the range of variables q and ϕ by one quarter of the elementary cell, i.e., $0 \leq q \leq e$ and $0 \leq \phi \leq \pi$. Thus, the values of $\varepsilon = E_0(q, \phi)/E_c$ are found on the corresponding grid within this cell.

The code [E0_data.bas](#) for calculating E_0 is written in the open-source programming language QB64 [3] and attached below.

E0_data.bas

```
' This program is for calculating the two lowest Bloch bands E(q,phi)
' in the Bloch transistor for arbitrary ratios of Ej1/Ej2 and (Ej1+Ej2)/Ec.
' The ranges of variables: 0 < q < e and 0 < phi < pi.
' (c) A. Zorin, Aug.1994 and (c) A. Zorin, March 2026

DECLARE FUNCTION ApprE (x, z#())
DECLARE FUNCTION det# (x#)
DECLARE SUB Bloch (q#, Np%)
Common Shared k#, q#, Np%, km2#
Const NpMax% = 305
Const NM% = 7 ' N_max
Const Acc# = 1E-12

Dim EoqArray(0 To 401)
'Dim V2D#(1001, 1001)
Dim Eo2D(401, 401) 'is the square matrix (1,...401; 1,...401)
' 200 points for the period of phi
Dim Shared E0#(-NpMax% To NpMax%)
Dim Shared E1#(-NpMax% To NpMax%)

Const pi = 3.1415926#
Open "C:\xxx.dat" For Append As #3'INSERT HERE the OUTPUT FILE NAME!

' PARAMETERS OF THE BLOCH TRANSISTOR
EJ0Ec = 2 ' EJ0/Ec = (Ej1 + Ej2)/Ec, i.e. 2*lambda
Ej1Ej2 = 1 / 0.8181818 ' a = 0.1 ' Ej1/Ej2
rEj2 = 1 / (Ej1Ej2 + 1) ' Ej2/EJ0
rEj1 = 1 - rEj2 ' Ej1/EJ0
Dphi# = pi / 400 ' step of phi from 0 to pi !

For Kphi% = 0 To 400
Print , Kphi%
phi# = Dphi# * Kphi%
EjEc = Sqr(rEj1 ^ 2 + rEj2 ^ 2 + 2 * rEj1 * rEj2 * Cos(phi#)) * EJ0Ec
q# = EjEc / 2 ' parameter q = EJ0/2Ec = 0.5(Ej1 + Ej2)/Ec
Np% = 300
Call Bloch(q#, Np%)
NvqU% = 400
NvqU2% = 200
dNvq% = 400
kStep = 1 / NvqU%
For Nkx% = 0 To NvqU% ' q loop
kx = Nkx% * kStep
arg = kx
d00# = ApprE(arg, E0#()) ' arg is q!
EoqArray(Nkx%) = d00#
Next Nkx%
For count% = 0 To NvqU%
Eo2D(Kphi% + 1, count% + 1) = EoqArray(count%)
Print #3, Eo2D(Kphi% + 1, count% + 1) ' THE OUTPUT in THE FILE
Next count%
Next Kphi%
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End
```

```

Function ApprE (x, z#()) Static
' This function makes approximation of arrays E0 and E1
' with the help of polynom of the 4th order.
' This approximation makes it possible to find values
' of E0 and E1 for arbitrary argumet, not necessarily
' on the grid.
' x is the vector (-1 : +1)
y = x
dy# = 1 / Np%
dy3# = dy# * dy# * dy#

i% = Int(y * Np%)
z1# = z#(i% - 1): z2# = z#(i%)
z3# = z#(i% + 1): z4# = z#(i% + 2)
y1# = (i% - 1) * dy#: y2# = i% * dy#
y3# = (i% + 1) * dy#: y4# = (i% + 2) * dy#
zy# = -(y - y2#) * (y - y3#) * (y - y4#) * z1# / 6
zy# = zy# + (y - y1#) * (y - y3#) * (y - y4#) * z2# / 2
zy# = zy# - (y - y1#) * (y - y2#) * (y - y4#) * z3# / 2
zy# = zy# + (y - y1#) * (y - y2#) * (y - y3#) * z4# / 6
zy# = zy# / dy3#
ApprE = zy#

```

End Function

```

Sub Bloch (q#, Np%) Static
' This subroutine calculates arrays of values for
' low (0) and upper (1) bands.
' q=Ej/2Ec, k is the double Bloch vector K (k=2K)
' Np% is the number of points within the interval [0,1]
ks# = 1 / Np%
For jk% = 0 To Np%
k# = ks# * jk%
'The 0th band
a1# = -2 * q# ' this boundaries are
au# = 1 ' for arbitrary q,
If q# > 3 Then au# = 6 - 1.504 * q# 'for q<300 at least!
20 d1# = det(a1#)
du# = det(au#)
40 am# = (a1# + au#) / 2
dm# = det(am#)
If Sgn(dm#) = Sgn(d1#) Then a1# = am# Else au# = am#
If Abs(au# - a1#) > Acc# Then 40
E0#(jk%) = am#
E0#(-jk%) = am#
'The 1st band
a1# = 1# ' this boundaries are
If q# > 3 Then a1# = 6 - 1.504 * q# ' for arbitrary q,
au# = 4# ' for q<300 at least!
If q# > 10 Then au# = 6 - q# ^ 2 / 70
21 d1# = det(a1#)
du# = det(au#)
41 am# = (a1# + au#) / 2
dm# = det(am#)
If Sgn(dm#) = Sgn(d1#) Then a1# = am# Else au# = am#
If Abs(au# - a1#) > Acc# Then 41
E1#(jk%) = am#
E1#(-jk%) = am#
Next jk%
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For jkd% = 1 To 5
E0#(Np% + jkd%) = E0#(-Np% + jkd%)
E0#(-Np% - jkd%) = E0#(Np% - jkd%)
E1#(Np% + jkd%) = E1#(-Np% + jkd%)
E1#(-Np% - jkd%) = E1#(Np% - jkd%)
Next jkd%
End Sub

```

```

Function det# (x#) Static
' Function gives the value of the determinant,
' x is a try value of eigenvalue E/Ec,
' and q=Ej/2Ec, k is the double Bloch vector K (k=2K)
a0# = x# - k# * k#
q2# = q# ^ 2
a1# = x# - (2 + k#) ^ 2
am1# = x# - (k# - 2) ^ 2
d1# = a0#

```

```

d2# = a0# * a1# - q2#
d4# = a0# * am1# - q2#
d5# = a0# * a1# * am1# - q2# * (a1# + am1#)
For n% = 1 To NM% - 1
  amn1# = x# - (k# - 2 * n% - 2) ^ 2
  apn1# = x# - (k# + 2 * n% + 2) ^ 2
  d3# = apn1# * d2# - q2# * d1#
  d6# = apn1# * d5# - q2# * d4#
  d7# = amn1# * d6# - q2# * d3#
  d4# = amn1# * d5# - q2# * d2#
  d1# = d5#
  d5# = d7#
  d2# = d6#
Next n%
det# = d5# ' the output value
End Function

```


Fig. 1. A quarter of the elementary cell of the ground-state-energy surface E_0 , found using computer code [Eo_matrix.bas](#). The Bloch transistor parameters for this plot are $\lambda = (E_{J1} + E_{J2})/2E_c = 1$ and $a = (E_{J1} - E_{J2})/(E_{J1} + E_{J2}) = 0.1$. As a proof of the code, the found minimum half-splitting energy, $\delta E/2 = (E_1 - E_0)/2$, is consistent with the value given by approximate formula $\delta E = E_J(e, \pi)/E_c = 2a\lambda$ which is valid in the limit of $E_J \ll E_c$ [3].

III. Finding the coefficients in Fourier-series representation of $E_0(q, \phi)$

The periodic even function E_0 can be represented as a double Fourier series (see Appendix A in Ref. [1]):

$$\varepsilon(\theta, \phi) = -0.25A_{00} - 0.5 \sum_{k \geq 1} A_{k0} \cos k\theta - 0.5 \sum_{m \geq 1} A_{0m} \cos m\phi - \sum_{k, m \geq 1} A_{km} \cos k\theta \cos m\phi, \quad (7)$$

where $\theta = \pi q/e$ is the dimensionless quasicharge. The Fourier coefficients in Eq. (7) are

$$A_{km} = -\frac{4}{\pi^2} \int_0^\pi \int_0^\pi \varepsilon(\theta, \phi) \cos k\theta \cos m\phi d\theta d\phi, \quad (8)$$

where integer numbers k and $m = 0, 1, 2, \dots$

Using the values of $\varepsilon(q, \phi)$ found on a sufficiently dense grid, matrix elements A_{km} (8) can be found by numerical integration. This is done with the help of the code [Element_Akm.bas](#).

Element_Akm.bas

```
' Calculating of coefficient A[k,m] (c) Zorin, April 2026

Dim Shared E2D$(401, 401)
Dim Shared A$(101, 101)

Open "C:\xxx.dat" For Input As #2 'INPUT OF DATA FOUND EARLIER BY "E0_data.bas"

k% = 2 ' input of k
m% = 1 ' input of m

pi# = 3.1415926535898
norm# = -4 / pi# / pi#
df# = pi# / 400
dq# = pi# / 400

For CountPhi% = 1 To 401
  Print CountPhi%
  For CountQ% = 1 To 401
    Input #2, E2D$(CountPhi%, CountQ%) 'INPUT
  Next CountQ%
Next CountPhi%

Sf# = 0
For CountPhi% = 0 To 399
  f# = CountPhi% * df#
  Print CountPhi%
  Sq# = 0
  For CountQ% = 0 To 399
    q# = CountQ% * dq#
    dSq# = Cos(k% * q#) * E2D$(CountPhi% + 1, CountQ% + 1) * dq#
    Sq# = Sq# + dSq#
  Next CountQ%
  dSf# = Cos(m% * f#) * Sq# * df#
  Sf# = Sf# + dSf#
Next CountPhi%
Sf# = norm# * Sf#
Akm# = Sf# ' is matrix element A[k,m]

Print Akm# ' OUTPUT
End
```

Several elements A_{km} found using code [Element_Akm.bas](#) are given below in the form of truncated matrix:

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} & 0.6037 & -0.0386 & 0.0094 & \dots \\ \mathbf{0.5055} & \mathbf{-0.0979} & 0.0237 & -0.0064 & \dots \\ -0.0685 & 0.0317 & -0.0126 & 0.0051 & \dots \\ 0.0193 & -0.0112 & 0.0067 & -0.0034 & \dots \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \end{bmatrix},$$

where matrix element A_{00} (giving an inessential additive constant for energy ε) is omitted.

IV. Deriving formula (57) for the first harmonic of periodic function $g(\phi)$

The 2π -periodic even function $g(\phi)$ is given by formula (32):

$$g(\phi) = \frac{0.5a}{\cos^2 \frac{\phi}{2} + a^2 \sin^2 \frac{\phi}{2}} - 0.5 \quad (9)$$

and its average value is

$$\bar{g} = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} \frac{0.5a}{\cos^2 \frac{\phi}{2} + a^2 \sin^2 \frac{\phi}{2}} d\phi - 0.5. \quad (10)$$

To prove that this value is zero, we find the definite integral:

$$\int_0^{\pi} \frac{0.5a}{\cos^2 \frac{\phi}{2} + a^2 \sin^2 \frac{\phi}{2}} d\phi = \int_0^{\pi} \frac{0.5a \sec^2 \frac{\phi}{2}}{1 + a^2 \tan^2 \frac{\phi}{2}} d\phi = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{1}{1+x^2} dx = \frac{\pi}{2}, \quad (11)$$

where we made substitution $x = a \tan(\phi/2)$, $dx = 0.5a \sec^2(\phi/2) d\phi$ with the new limits of integration, i.e., $\phi = 0 \rightarrow x = 0$ and $\phi = \pi \rightarrow x = \infty$. Thus, the average value $\bar{g} = 0$.

The amplitude of the first harmonic g_1 of function $g(\phi)$ is given by the integral

$$g_1 = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} \frac{0.5a \cos \phi}{\cos^2 \frac{\phi}{2} + a^2 \sin^2 \frac{\phi}{2}} d\phi = \frac{a}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} \frac{\cos^2 \frac{\phi}{2} - \sin^2 \frac{\phi}{2}}{\cos^2 \frac{\phi}{2} + a^2 \sin^2 \frac{\phi}{2}} d\phi = \frac{2a}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi/2} \frac{1 - \tan^2 x}{1 + a^2 \tan^2 x} dx, \quad (12)$$

where we made substitution $x = \phi/2$, $d\phi = 2dx$ and correspondingly changed the upper limit, $\pi \rightarrow \pi/2$. Making new substitution $y = \tan x$, $dy = \sec^2 x dx$, and $dx = dy/(1+y^2)$ and inserting the new integration limits: $x = 0 \rightarrow y = 0$ and $x = \pi/2 \rightarrow y = \infty$, we obtain

$$g_1 = \left(\frac{2a}{\pi} \right) \int_0^{\infty} \frac{1-y^2}{(1+a^2 y^2)(1+y^2)} dy = \left(\frac{2a}{\pi} \right) \int_0^{\infty} \left(\frac{A}{1+y^2} + \frac{B}{1+a^2 y^2} \right) dy, \quad (13)$$

where $A = 2/(1-a^2)$ and $B = -(1+a^2)/(1-a^2)$. Finally, the result reads:

$$g_1 = \left(\frac{2a}{\pi} \right) \left[A \frac{\pi}{2} + B \frac{\pi}{2a} \right] = aA + B = \frac{1-a}{1+a} = r, \quad (14)$$

that gives the first harmonic component equal to

$$[g(\phi)]_{\omega} = r \cos \phi, \quad (15)$$

i.e., the expression identical to Eq. (57) in Ref. [1].

References

1. A. B. Zorin, Dual Shapiro steps and fundamental transconductance in dc driven Bloch transistor, arXiv:2605.14080 [cond-mat.supr-con], <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2605.14080>
2. K. K. Likharev and A. B. Zorin, Theory of the Bloch-wave oscillations in small Josephson junctions, *Journal of Low Temp. Phys.* **59**, 347–382 (1985).
3. Programming language QB64, <https://qb64.com/>